

A New Method to Scrutinize a Windows Jump List from Portable Applications

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Abstract -- The examination and usage of Jump Lists structure of Windows 7 has attracted forensic and investigation application for capturing the user activity on a system. However, the observation of the Jump Lists by portable application is very limited. This paper proposed a new methodology to scrutinize the behavior of Windows Jump List (WJL) by opening and editing a system's local file on executing portable applications. The experiment included the creation of Windows 7 and later versions, using Virtual Machine and installation of Portable Office Editor on Removable device. These portable applications included "JartePortable" and "FocusWriterPortable" for opening and editing a .docx file respectively, and "PDF-XchangeViewerPortable" for opening / editing a .pdf file residing on local system. Additionally, this approach notifies the impact of opening a local file from removable device on associated application's WJL and it has significant importance in an anti-forensic scenario where a user tries to modify a system's local files through a portable application. Experiments show successfully on several artifacts, that holds information on Jump Lists, including; Jump List entry, MAC Timestamp, File size and Entry Modified Timestamp. The results show that a user can bypass the Windows Jump lists by accessing system's local files through portable applications from removable external storage device.

Index Terms -- Jump Lists, Windows Server, Portable application, Removable device, Digital forensics

1. INTRODUCTION

Jump List is a unique Taskbar and Start menu feature introduced by Microsoft in Windows 7 and is included in Windows 8 and Windows 10. Jump Lists are created by Operating System (OS) when a user performs certain actions using different applications, such as creating and saving a file using Microsoft Word, browsing the internet or opening existing files of the system, etc. This feature shows a number of opened files with a left click on the application icon pinned to Start or Taskbar menu. Unlike Windows 10, Windows 7 and 8 offers the users to customize the number of items to be displayed on the respective application's Jump list by altering its Registry value [1].

The Jump Lists formed are automatically saved as an *.automaticDestinations-ms or a *.customDestinations-ms file, that allows the user to quickly access the recently opened application files. It is believed that these locations hold valuable information which may help during a forensic examination of the system [2]. Windows Jump Lists (WJL) hold a significant value for any study that includes the analysis and examination of a user's activity

on a system. If WJL are examined from a user's perspective, they simply increase the level of productivity by enabling the user to have a quick access to his files/tasks, and to the associated applications. Whereas, if examined from a Forensics' angle, they can be a good indicator of recently opened or accessed files / applications / websites [3].

Before the introduction of Jump List feature, forensic analysis was made possible by using the information from Most Recently Used (MRU) and Most Frequently Used (MFU) items residing in the Windows Registry [2]. In contrast to MRU and MFU list, jump list can exhibit substantial amount of information regarding user's activity on the system from a Forensic analysis viewpoint. Upon analysis, Jump Lists can reveal vital information regarding files accesses, file and volume names, file size, file path, MAC (Modified, Accessed, and Created) timestamps, and any record made through uploading or downloading of file using web browsers. These artifacts are observed to persist even after the local files and their respective applications have been deleted from the system [4].

The WJL configuration files are a source of evidence while taking user's activity in account. With all the vital information they carry, they can be relied upon while investigating the course of action that was taken by the user on a system that is under observation. The existing work on analysis of WJL has been carried out on jump lists created as a result of executing an application (program) that is locally hosted on the system under observation. However, there is little to no work that can be found on the analysis of WJL formed after running an application from a removable device.

In this research effort, an inventive way has been presented to investigate the effect caused on WJL by executing portable applications from a removable device. This effect is further examined by opening / editing / saving local files of the system through portable applications in Windows 7, 8, and 10, and Windows Server 2012, mainly. The observations are verified by using various Forensic analysis tools.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II gives the background information; Section III describes the methodology. Section IV explains the observations and results; section V presents the discussion on results and section VI concludes the paper.

II. BACKGROUND INFORMATION

The Windows Jump Lists (WJL) are aimed to provide users with rapid access to the files and different tasks that are associated with their respective applications [5]. WJL can be thought of as a start menu that is application specific, as they are located on the Windows Start menu under the recent file section or on the currently running programs on the Taskbar. Another location of WJL is on the applications that are pinned to the Start menu or the Taskbar and are found with a right click on the icon of the application as depicted in Figure 1. Both these WJLs have different appearances, but they serve the same purpose.

The record maintenance in JWJL for each application is done in a circular data structure that deletes the oldest entry of the list while a new document is opened if the jump list space gets full [6].

Fig 1. Jump List Example Associated with Adobe Acrobat

The Jump list files that are saved as AutomaticDestinations files are located in the following path [7]:

`"C:\Users\%USERNAME%\AppData\Roaming\Microsoft\Windows\Recent\AutomaticDestinations"`

These files are automatically created by the Shell when a user performs any action on the system, or in other words these types of files are created and maintained by the OS. They keep a record of the usage of data file by sorting the items as *Most Recently Used* (MRU) or *Most Frequently Used* (MFU). The Jump list files that are saved as CustomDestinations files, are located in the path [7]:

`"C:\Users\%USERNAME%\AppData\Roaming\Microsoft\Windows\Recent\CustomDestinations"`

These files are created and maintained by the application itself. Both of these Jump List file types depend on the SHLLINK structure for the storage of most of their data [8]. It is observed that the programs that are pinned to the Start Menu can be accessed at the path:

`"C:\Users\USERNAME\AppData\Roaming\Microsoft\InternetExplorer\QuickLaunch\UserPinned"`

And, the shortcuts at the taskbar can be accessed at the path;

`"C:\Users\USERNAME\AppData\Roaming\Microsoft\InternetExplorer\QuickLaunch\UserPinned\TaskB"`

Name of each of the Jump List file type, i.e., the Destination Filename, starts with a long and extensive

string of characters, referred to as the Application ID, or simply "AppID" [2]. `d00655d2aa12ff6d.automaticDestinations-ms` for example, is the AppID for MS Power Point application. It is a 16-character name which classifies the specific application or its version which is used to access a particular file or resource.

Where WJL provides quick and easy access by recording the activities performed by a user, they can also be a challenge for the user's privacy working in a shared environment. For this reason, Microsoft provides the option to delete data from the Jump List, where the recent entries can simply be removed with a right click on the entries in the list and selecting the "Remove from the list" option.

The entries in the application's Jump List are also maintained in the respective Jump List configuration file. Lyness R. mentions in his article [2] that removing the data from Taskbar or Start menu Jump List does not remove entries from the Jump List configuration files. Carvey H. [9] discusses in his blog that the data in these configuration files lasts even after their respective applications have been deleted from the system. Larson [4] mentions in his work that these artifacts are found to be preserved even after the associated files and applications are deleted from the system.

Harjinder et al. [10] have highlighted the entries made in the Jump List configuration file whenever a file is created, modified or accessed. All these entries can reveal vital information about the user's activity. Antonovich C. [11] has worked on the retrieval of the deleted Jump List data and was able to retrieve it partially for the Windows 8 but no data was retrieved for Windows 7. Singh et al. [1] have demonstrated the impact of normal and private browsing with a local browser on the respective Jump Lists. In another paper, Singh et al. [12] have discussed a methodology to retrieve deleted jump list entries for Windows 10. Their results coincide with Larson's findings [4].

III. EXPERIMENTS AND METHODOLOGY

This section discusses the experimental goals, methodology and the observations and analysis done on the jump lists in Windows 7, 8, 10 and Windows Server 12 system.

A. EXPERIMENTAL GOALS

The prime objective of this experiment was to observe the impact of 1) opening a system's local file from removable media application 2) editing a local file using removable media application on the related Windows Jump lists.

B. FORENSIC ANALYSIS PROCESS

It is essential to discuss the process of Forensic analysis of WJL first. In this study, this process was carried out into the following three phases;

i. Data Generation

As a first step in this phase, a list containing the steps to generate data was made, in order to follow same procedure on all the OS. Next, Windows 7 VM was started and a file was created and saved using Microsoft Word processor. For further experimentation, a .pdf file was downloaded from the Internet and was opened on the system to generate an entry in the specific Jump List of Adobe Reader. The portable applications were run from the removable device and these saved files were accessed via these applications.

Same procedure was followed on Windows 8, Windows 10 and Windows Server 2012 VM. Table 1 shows the list of software that were used to generate data for the Jump Lists;

TABLE 1. SOFTWARE USED TO GENERATE DATA FOR WINDOWS JUMP LISTS

Software	Identifier	Description
Microsoft Word	Word	Word Processor, Distributed by Microsoft
Adobe Acrobat Reader	Adobe Reader	Document Reader/Generator, Distributed by Adobe Acrobat

The portable applications, which were run from the removable device to analyze their effect on the Jump Lists, are shown in table 2.

TABLE 2. PORTABLE APPLICATIONS EXECUTED FROM REMOVABLE DEVICE

Portable Application	Description
PDF-XChangeViewerPortable	Portable application for viewing/editing .pdf documents
JartePortable	Portable application for viewing, creating or editing word documents
FocusWriterPortable	Portable application for creating word documents

The table 3 shows the list of the equipment and the Forensic tools that were used to carry out the study and the analysis of the Windows Jump Lists.

ii. Data Collection

After the data generation phase, the data for study was collected from the VMs of Windows 7, 8, 10 and Windows Server 2012. For the data collection, the images of the concerned files were taken by using FTK Imager. The Jump List configuration files were opened through FTK Imager and Jump List extract tools to

study the behavior of the Jump Lists after the applied actions.

TABLE 3. TOOLS USED FOR FORENSIC ANALYSIS OF WINDOWS JUMP LISTS

Item	Identifier	Description
Workstation	Workstation	Microsoft Windows 10 Pro
VMWare Workstation Pro	VMware	Emulates VMs for Windows 7, Windows 8, Windows 10 and Windows Server 2012
FTK® Imager v3.4.2.6	FTK Imager	Creates Images for VMs
Jumplist File Extract	JumpList FE	Extracts Jump List data
JumpLISTER v1.1.0	JumpLISTER	Extracts Jump List data
JumpListsView	JumpListsView	Extracts Jump List data
DCode v4.02a	Date Decoder	Converts Data to Date/Time Values

iii. Data Analysis

After the data collection step, the data in the Jump Lists configuration files were analyzed for potential record of any activity on that system. Forensic analysis tools, FTK Imager was used to create the image of the Disk for analysis and Jump Lists data was extracted using three Jump List tools, Jumplist File Extract, Jumplister and Jump List view. Analysis was performed on the AutomaticDestinations-ms and CustomDestinations-ms files generated by the up mentioned applications. The findings are given in the next chapter of this report. To interpret the Hexadecimal value of Time Stamp, Dcode, an open source tool was used.

C. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND TESTING

To carry out the analysis on the WJL, Windows 7, 8, 10 and Windows Server 2012 were installed on Virtual machines. Emulation was created for these Operating Systems. Further, Microsoft office was installed and by using Word application, a document was created and saved on the machine. For further analysis, Adobe acrobat reader was installed and a .pdf file was downloaded from the internet and saved on the system. The purpose of all these actions was to generate Jump Lists for these applications, as well as to make entries in the Jump List Configuration File. In the experiments, FTK Imager 3.4.2.6 was used to acquire the image of the associated Jump List files.

To investigate the effect caused on Jump Lists by executing portable applications from a removable device,

Portable Office Editor and Portable PDF Viewer / Editor, were first installed on the Removable device and were then executed using Windows 7, 8 and 10 and Windows Server 2012.

In this context, few tests were carried out in Windows 7, 8, 10 and Server 2012 by opening and editing the local files stored on the system from removable device with portable applications installed on them.

Test 1: Opening a System's Local File through Portable Application

To carry out this experiment, the Jump List configuration file for MS Word was deleted manually from the System. The purpose for this deletion was to check how a new Jump List configuration file is created after accessing the local file of the system via portable application installed in a removable device. The path for the MS Word Jump List Configuration file for the system under study was;

C:\Users\username\AppData\Roaming\Microsoft\Windows\Recent\AutomaticDestinations\fb3b0dbfee58fac8.automaticDestinations-ms

A local file, named "Portable check.docx" residing on the machine, was accessed through portable application installed on the removable device.

The portable tools, "FocusWriterPortable" and "JartePortable" were used to open this file. After closing the applications and unplugging the removable device, the jump list of MS Word was opened with a right click on the Taskbar Icon. In addition to this, image of the disk was created using FTK Imager and tools were used to extract

Jump List configuration files. The WJL on the taskbar after opening the file from Portable application, is shown in the figure 2.

Figure 2. Jump List after opening a local file 'Portable check.docx' from Portable Application

Test 2: Editing a System's Local File through Portable Application

A file, named "Sun.docx", was created and saved on the local system using MS Word application running on same system. The WJL entry that was created by this file was then extracted with the help of *Jumplist File Extract* tool.

Figure 3 shows the extracts of the word file "Sun.docx". The other jump list tools were also used to verify the observation. The fields are clearly revealing the MAC Timestamp of the file, which are also highlighted in the Hex extracts of the file shown in figure 4 along with Long and Short name, Volume Guid, File Object ID and Path info. The file Size field can also be observed. In the Hex extracts the "File Size" entry comes right after the MAC Timestamps which is highlighted in figure 4.

Long Name	Short Name	Modified	Created	Accessed	File S...	Machi...	Volume Guid	File Object ID	Path Info
D:\MSIS\for thesis\Sun.docx	Sun.docx	2016/05/19, 11:27:35	2016/05/19, 11:27:35	2016/05/19, 11:27:35	11457	adeel	A8E445C8-B619-4DD8-97F0-A0EA90267...	F5D248A5-1B2B-11E6-8806-3C970E6034...	D:\MSIS\for thesis\Sun.docx

Figure 3. Jump List file extracts after the creation of file 'Sun.docx' using MS Word Application

Address	Hex Data	ASCII Data
800	4C 00 00 00 01 14 02 00-00 00 00 00 C0 00 00 00	L À
810	00 00 00 46 83 00 A0 00-20 00 00 00 D5 B5 31 88	...F.....Ôul
820	97 B1 D1 01 F8 C8 44 88-97 B1 D1 01 F8 C8 44 88	±Ñ øÈD...±Ñ øÈD
830	97 B1 D1 01 C1 2C 00 00-00 00 00 00 01 00 00 00	±Ñ À,
840	00 00 00 00 00 00 00 00-00 00 00 00 65 01 14 00e.....
850	1F 50 E0 4F D0 20 EA 3A-69 10 A2 D8 08 00 2B 30	-PàOD é:i-øø...+0
860	30 9D 19 00 2F 44 3A 5C-00 00 00 00 00 00 00 00	0.../D:\.....
870	00 00 00 00 00 00 00 00-00 00 00 00 4E 00 31 00 00N-1.....
880	00 00 00 91 47 90 28 10-00 4D 53 49 53 00 00 3AG-(-MSIS...
890	00 09 00 04 00 EF BE 16-47 2C 9C B3 48 4E 2F 2EI%G, 'HN/.
8a0	00 00 00 85 02 00 00 00-00 04 00 00 00 00 00 00
8b0	00 00 00 00 00 00 00 00-00 86 17 68 00 4D 00 53h-M-S

Figure 4. Jump List file extracts after the Word File 'Sun.docx' creation

Long Name	Short Name	Modified	Created	Accessed	File S...	Machi...	Volume Guid	File Object ID	Path Info
D:\MSIS\for thesis\Sun.docx	Sun.docx	2016/05/19, 11:27:35	2016/05/19, 11:27:35	2016/05/19, 11:27:35	11457	adeel	A8E445C8-B619-4DDB-97F0-A0EA90267...	F3D248A5-1B2B-11E6-8806-3C970E6034...	D:\MSIS\for thesis\Sun.docx

Figure 5. Jump List file extracts after editing via Portable Application

800	4C	00	00	00	01	14	02	00-00	00	00	00	C0	00	00	00	L	-----A---
810	00	00	00	46	83	00	A0	00-20	00	00	00	D5	B5	31	88	---F--- --Oul-	
820	97	B1	D1	01	F8	C8	44	88-97	B1	D1	01	F8	C8	44	88	±Ñ·øÈD·±Ñ·øÈD-	
830	97	B1	D1	01	C1	2C	00	00-00	00	00	00	01	00	00	00	±Ñ·Á,	
840	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00-00	00	00	00	83	01	14	00	-----e---	
850	1F	50	E0	4F	D0	20	EA	3A-69	10	A2	D8	08	00	2B	30	·PàOÐ ê:i·e0·+0	
860	30	9D	19	00	2F	44	3A	5C-00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	0	---/D:\-----
870	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00-00	00	00	00	4E	00	31	00	00	-----N-1--
880	00	00	00	91	47	90	28	10-00	4D	53	49	53	00	00	3A	---G-(·MSIS·:	
890	00	09	00	04	00	EF	BE	16-47	2C	9C	B3	48	4E	2F	2E	-----i¼·G,·³HN/.	
8a0	00	00	00	85	02	00	00	00-00	04	00	00	00	00	00	00	-----	
8b0	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00-00	86	17	68	00	4D	00	53	-----h·M·S	
8c0	00	49	00	53	00	00	00	14-00	60	00	31	00	00	00	00	-----I·S-----·-1----	

Figure 6. Jump List file extracts after editing the Word File

This file was then accessed through the portable application installed on removable device. Portable Office Editor “FocusWriterPortable” has compatibility with MS Word and can open .docx files. Using this tool, the file “Sun.docx” was opened and changings were made to the contents of the document, which were saved later using the same portable editor. The edited document and the Portable application were then closed, and Removable device was unplugged from the machine. The Jump List and its configuration file were reopened using FTK Imager and Jump List file extract tools, to observe the changes made in the record. The Jump List configuration file after editing through portable application is shown in the figure 5.

Similar procedure was followed for the Adobe Acrobat file. A .pdf file was downloaded from the internet and it was accessed through “PDF-XchangeViewerPortable” installed in removable device. Changes were made to the file and Jump List configuration file was extracted using forensic analysis tools.

IV. OBSERVATION AND FINDINGS

After the tests were carried out, comparison was made between the contents of the Jump List configuration file, before and after editing through Portable application. The following exceptional observations were made in Windows 7, 8, 10 and Windows Server 2012;

A. JUMP LISTS IDS

Every application installed on the machine generates either an AutomaticDestinations File type or a

CustomDestinations File type, which depends on the type of the application being run. The table 4 shows the observed Jump List IDs of the applications that were used in this study for the analysis purpose.

Different applications were opened and run on Windows 7, 8 and 10 and on Windows Server 2012, to observe any difference in the AppIDs maintained by these OS. The findings are given in table 5.

B. JUMP LIST ENTRY

Whenever a file is opened on a system using any application, it creates an entry in its respective Jump List configuration file. To analyze the Jump List entry made by “Portable check.docx” file, the already existing Jump List entry of this file from WJL of MS Word was first manually deleted, after which the same file was accessed via portable application from the removable device.

Typically, such an action creates an entry in the Jump List but to a surprise, the Jump List was found to be empty as shown on figure 2. To trace this activity, another effort was made by extracting the Jump List configuration file by using FTK Imager and JumpList File Extract. It was observed that after the deletion of the Jump List configuration file, the entry of this file was not made in the list of AutomaticDestinations files even after the file was accessed again through portable application.

TABLE 4. JUMP LIST IDS OF APPLICATIONS IN WINDOWS 10

Application	Jump List File Type	File Name
Adobe Reader	AutomaticDestinations	de48a32edcbe79e4.automaticDestinations-ms
Notepad	AutomaticDestinations	9b9cdc69c1c24e2b.automaticDestinations-ms
Google Chrome	CustomDestinations	5d696d521de238c3.customDestinations-ms
Power Point	AutomaticDestinations	d00655d2aa12ff6d.automaticDestinations-ms
Internet Explorer	CustomDestinations	28c8b86deab549a1.customDestinations-ms

TABLE 5. COMPARISON OF APPIDS IN DIFFERENT OS

Application	Windows 7	Windows 8	Windows 10	Windows Server 2012
	Application IDs			
Adobe Reader	de48a32edcbe79e4.automaticDestinations-ms	Same as Windows 7	Same as Windows 7	ff103e2cc310d0d.automaticDestinations-ms
Notepad	9b9cdc69c1c24e2b.automaticDestinations-ms	Same as Windows 7	Same as Windows 7	Same as Windows 7
Internet Explorer	28c8b86deab549a1.CutomDestinations-ms	Same as Windows 7	Same as Windows 7	Same as Windows 7
Chrome	5d696d521de238c3.customDestinations-ms	Same as Windows 7	Same as Windows 7	Same as Windows 7
Paint	12dc1ea8e34b5a6.automaticDestinations-ms	Same as Windows 7	Same as Windows 7	Same as Windows 7

C. MAC TIMESTAMPS

The MAC Timestamps are the first fields to be observed in order to detect any activity on the system under investigation. In Figure 6, the MAC timestamps of the file “Sun.docx” as per the Jump List Configuration File are shown in table 6.

Table 6. MAC Timestamps for file “Sun.docx”

Created Time Stamp	D5 B5 31 88 97 B1 D1 01 Thu, 19 May 2016 11:27:35 UTC +05:00
Accessed Time Stamp	F8 C8 44 88 97 B1 D1 01 Thu, 19 May 2016 11:27:35 UTC +05:00
Modified Time Stamp	F8 C8 44 88 97 B1 D1 01 Thu, 19 May 2016 11:27:35 UTC +05:00

These Hex values that are decoded using DCode Tool, are highlighted in the figure 4 as well. After editing the file “Sun.docx” through portable application, it was expected that the MAC Timestamps of the file will also update. This is because, the Modified and the Accessed Timestamps are changed whenever a file is opened and edited. To find this difference, the Jump List Configuration file was extracted once again using

Forensic Analysis Tools and MAC Timestamp entries / fields were checked and compared with the former values for the predictable modifications.

Unexpectedly, the MAC Timestamp, before and after the access of the file through portable application, was observed to be unchanged. The Modified and Accessed Timestamp fields should have updated as the file was opened and edited. But surprisingly, no record of these actions in the Jump List configuration file was found.

D. FILE SIZE

The entry next to MAC Timestamp refers to the “File Size”. When the file “Sun.docx” was created the file size according to the Jump List file extracts was;

File Size in Hexadecimal	File Size in Decimal
C1 2C	11457

These values are highlighted in the Jump List file extracts as shown in the figures 4 and 5. After the file was edited, the Jump List configuration file was extracted again using Forensic analysis tools, as shown

in figure 7, and a comparison was made between the two extracts.

Figure 7. Jump List file extracts with highlighted File Size after editing the Word File

It was expected that the “File Size” must have changed after editing the file, but the Jump List File extracts depicted contrary to this. The File size before and after the editing as per Jump List Configuration file extracts appeared to be same which is very unlikely.

E. ENTRY MODIFIED TIMESTAMP

Another value that changes in the Jump List Configuration file whenever a file is accessed / edited, is the “Entry Modified” Timestamp. When the system’s local file “Lesson 2.pdf” was accessed via Portable application, it was expected that the Entry Modified Timestamp will update, to check this, jump list configuration file was extracted using FTK imager that is shown in the figure 8. Surprisingly, this Timestamp like the MAC Timestamp was unchanged even the file was accessed through portable application installed on removable device.

Figure 8. Jump List file extracts with highlighted Entry Modified Timestamp after opening system’s Local file via portable application

V. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The experiments carried out in section 3, aimed at detecting the modifications in WJL configuration file if system’s local file was accessed from a portable application installed on a removable device. The findings of *Test 1*, as shown in section 4, demonstrate that opening a local file from removable media (with a compatible application) does not create a Jump List entry. Similarly, no modification is recorded in the MAC Timestamps of the experimented file. The result of *Test 2* reveals that editing a local file, with a portable application installed on removable device, does not modify MAC Timestamps, entry modified Timestamp and size of the file in the associated jump list configuration file.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

From an analyst's viewpoint, Jump Lists is a feature and an artifact that needs to be explored and understood even more.

However, at this moment, all the research and exploration that has been conducted reveals that a considerable amount of valuable information is present and hidden in these artifacts. This information can be useful during a system’s analysis while making timeline of events that are tied to actions of a specific user. This research effort aimed at exploring Windows Jump List when Portable applications were run from removable device. For this purpose, local file from the system were opened, edited and saved using Portable Applications. After these actions, Removable device was unplugged, and Jump Lists were analyzed for potential evidence created as a result of these actions. Forensic analysis tools, *FTK Imager* was used to create the image of the Disk for analysis and Jump Lists data was extracted using three Jump List tools, *Jumplist File Extract*, *Jumplister* and *Jump List view*.

Surprisingly, there was no updated data in the Windows Jump Lists, which was verified through above mentioned tools. No entries were made in the Jump Lists regarding, the recently opened files, the editing done to those files, as well as the changes that were saved. In other words, the OS was unable to register any changes to the Jump Lists via Portable applications running from removable device. It is a loophole in the functioning of the Jump Lists that can be exploited by an unauthorized user. The severity of this gap is even more critical on the Windows Server, as any suspicious user can access the system’s data without being getting noticed, only by plugging the removable device and running portable application with no fear of “Jump Lists”.

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